

Studies on the Solvent Effect and Assignment of Bands of the Absorption Spectra of some Phenol Betaines. Part I

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Absorption spectra of N-methyl-2-(*p*-hydroxy phenyl) quinolinium hydroxide anhydro-salt has been studied in different solvents in the region 200–600 $m\mu$. Four bands at 20830, 27400, 32470, and 42020 cm^{-1} have been observed in its ethanolic solution. A marked relation between the absorption spectra and hydrogen bonding capacity of the solvent has been observed in the case of the anhydro-salt characteristic absorption band in the region of longer wave-lengths. Based on available evidences, the band at 20830 cm^{-1} has been assigned to an intra-molecular charge-transfer band. Bands at 27400, 32470 and 42020 cm^{-1} have been assigned to ${}^1L_b \rightarrow {}^1A$, ${}^1L_a \rightarrow {}^1A$ and ${}^1B_b \rightarrow {}^1A$ transitions respectively.

N-methyl-2-(*p*-hydroxy phenyl) quinolinium hydroxide anhydro-salt was prepared by the method described by Saxena *et al.*¹. The compound is obtained as crystalline orange needles, m.p. 85.5°. The betaine is found to be basic in nature and forms colourless salts with acids. No systematic study of the absorption spectra of the phenol betaines derived from 2-(hydroxy phenyl) substituted quinoline has been reported so far. Recently Tandon *et al.*² and authors³ have reported the studies on the absorption spectra of some other phenol betaines of quinoline and pyridine series. In the present communication a detailed study of the absorption spectra of N-methyl-2-(*p*-hydroxy phenyl) quinolinium hydroxide anhydro-salt in different solvents has been made.

EXPERIMENTAL

All the measurements have been carried out on the Unicam S.P. 500 spectrophotometer, and centred around 25°. Plots of molar extinction coefficient against wave-numbers for the observed bands of N-methyl-2-(*p*-hydroxy phenyl) quinolinium hydroxide anhydro-salt in (1) chloroform and (2) ethanol are given in figure 1. Characteristics of different bands have been tabulated in Table I.

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2. S. P. Tandon, *et al.*, *Indian J. Pure and Applied Phys.*, 1968, 6, 694.
3. J. P. Saxena, *et al.* (communicated).

Fig. 1

Absorption spectra of *N*-methyl-2-(*p*-hydroxy phenyl) quinolinium hydroxide, anhydro salt in (1) chloroform and (2) ethanol.

TABLE I

Characteristics and assignment of the bands of the absorption spectra of N-methyl-2-(p-hydroxy phenyl) quinolinium hydroxide anhydro-salt.

Band	Solvent	Band position		Intensity		Assignment
		m μ	cm $^{-1}$	ϵ_{max}	f^*	
I	Benzene	543	18420	12590	—	Intra-molecular charge-transfer band.
	Chloroform	538	18590	19050	.314	
	Ethanol	480	20830	13800	.200	
II	Chloroform	365	27400	6918	.134	$^1L_b \rightarrow ^1A$
	Ethanol	365	27400	4365	.074	
III	Chloroform	313	31950	6918	.185	$^1L_a \rightarrow ^1A$
	Ethanol	308	32470	6918	.218	
IV	Ethanol	238	42020	20890	.475	$^1B_b \rightarrow ^1A$

* f values have been estimated using Jorgensen's formula.

DISCUSSION

N-methyl 2-(*p*-hydroxy phenyl) quinolinium hydroxide anhydro-salt exists in the following resonating forms (a) and (b).

There is a preponderance of the forms (a) over the form (b) as it accounts more readily for the di-polar nature and deep colour of the betaine.

Hydrocarbon naphthalene is chosen as the parent compound for the sake of comparison of its spectra^{4,5} with that of the betaine. Replacement of one methine group = CH- in naphthalene by nitrogen = N- affords the π -isoelectronic compound quinoline. Absorption spectra of π isoelectronic compounds are known to have similar general features⁶. The prominent difference in the spectra of aza aromatic compound quinoline from the spectra of corresponding aromatic hydrocarbon naphthalene lies in the greater intensity and partial loss of vibrational structure of the ${}^1L_b \rightarrow {}^1A$ band⁵, both these facts are attributed to the reduced symmetry of the aza aromatic compound as compared with the parent hydrocarbon. Intensities of ${}^1L_a \rightarrow {}^1A$ and ${}^1B_b \rightarrow {}^1A$ bands decrease in quinoline. Substitution of phenyl group in position 2 in quinoline will result a bathochromic shift of ${}^1B_b \rightarrow {}^1A$ and ${}^1L_b \rightarrow {}^1A$ bands. The vibrational structure is expected to be absent. Intensity of ${}^1L_b \rightarrow {}^1A$ band is expected to increase^{7,9}. Further substitution of anionic oxygen in *p*-position of phenyl ring and addition of CH_3 at nitrogen atom results into the desired compound N-methyl 2-(*p*-hydroxy phenyl) quinolinium hydroxide anhydro-salt. The effect of these substituents will be to produce a general bathochromic shift and hyperchromic effect.

The most striking feature in the absorption spectra of phenol betaine under study is the appearance of a new high intensity band in the longer wave-length region, which is absent in the parent compounds naphthalene, quinoline and phenyl quinoline. Behaviour of this band can be explained by comparing the spectra of phenol betaine with the spectra of N-oxides of pyridine and quinoline^{8,9}, in which case also similar effects have been observed.

The ground state of the phenol betaine under study may be considered as the resonance hybrid of the two structures (a) and (b). The ground state of the compound involving such a polar structure is considerably stabilized by polar solvents and by general electrostatic effects, as well as by the hydrogen bonding with the anionic oxygen⁹. The bathochromic shift of the ${}^1B_b \rightarrow {}^1A$ ($\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$) transition indicates that the π^* level is less stabilized by the polar solvents and since the excited state must also receive its predominant contribution from the polar structure (a), the difference between the ground and excited state is expected to lie predominantly on hydrogen bonding, but the greatly reduced hydrogen-bonding in the excited state would imply that the structure (b) is more important and that the oxygen atom has lost much or most of its charge. Thus the long wave-length band of N-methyl-2-(*p*-hydroxy phenyl) quinolinium hydroxide anhydro-salt which appears at $480 \text{ m}\mu$ ($\epsilon_{\text{max}} = 13800$) in ethanol, may be assigned to an intra-molecular charge-transfer band.

When hydrogen bonding with the oxygen anion occurs in hydroxylic solvents, the bands are shifted back to blue and practically coincide with those of the parent compound

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in acidic medium. This is what has been observed when ethanol is used as the solvent. Similar effects are reported in the case of N-oxides of pyridine and quinoline^{9,10}. Since the dipole moment of the phenol betaine is expected to decrease due to dipole-dipole interaction, the absorption bands will be shifted to the shorter wave-lengths with the increase of the polarity of the solvent^{5,11}.

Assignments of the bands : Band I : This band is observed at 543 m μ ($\epsilon_{\max} = 12590$) in benzene, which is shifted to 538 m μ ($\epsilon_{\max} = 19050$) in chloroform (polar solvent) and to 480 m μ ($\epsilon_{\max} = 13800$) in ethanol. The shift towards shorter wavelengths and the decrease in intensity in ethanol was expected due to hydrogen bonding. This band has been assigned to an intra-molecular charge-transfer band. In the parent compound no such band is observed.

Band II : In the case of naphthalene this band is observed at 311 m μ ($\epsilon_{\max} = 320$) and in quinoline at 314 m μ ($\epsilon_{\max} = 3000$) in ethanol. In case of the phenol betaine under study this band is observed at 365 m μ ($\epsilon_{\max} = 4365$) in ethanol and at 365 m μ ($\epsilon_{\max} = 6918$) in chloroform. This has been attributed to the effect of substituents on the naphthalene molecule, causing a bathochromic shift and the loss of vibrational structure. Using Platt's notations this band has been assigned to ${}^1L_b \rightarrow {}^1A$ transition.

Band III : In naphthalene this band is observed at 275 m μ ($\epsilon_{\max} = 5600$) and in quinoline at 278 m μ ($\epsilon_{\max} = 3500$). In the case of the betaine under study this band is observed at 308 m μ in ethanol and at 313 m μ in chloroform. The bathochromic and the hyperchromic effects observed are attributed to the effect of substituents, as before. Using Platt's notations this band has been assigned to ${}^1L_a \rightarrow {}^1A$ transition.

Band IV : In the case of naphthalene this band is observed at 221 m μ ($\epsilon_{\max} = 95500$) and in quinoline at 225 m μ ($\epsilon_{\max} = 35000$). In the phenol betaine under study the band is observed at 238 m μ in ethanol. As before the effect of substituents in the naphthalene moiety has caused a bathochromic shift. This band has been assigned to ${}^1B_b \rightarrow {}^1A$ transition.

The intensities of different bands and the effect of solvents are in conformity with these assignments given.

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